

INVESTIGATION OF THE MECHANISMS OF FUZZBALL FORMATION AND GROWTH IN AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT (AFP) OF THERMOSET COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work we investigated the fundamental mechanisms behind fuzzball formation in Automated Fiber Placement (AFP), leveraging an Electroimpact AFP 4.0 cell. The goal was to develop a deeper understanding of the sources of imperfections that degrade the mechanical performance of composite components fabricated via AFP. To this end, we achieved direct observation of fuzzball formation by integrating an optical microscope into the AFP end effector. These observations revealed that most fuzz accumulation occurs in the feeding channel section. To further study the phenomenon, we developed a dedicated AFP workbench that allows for controlled material feeding under variable prepreg tension. Using this setup, we examined fuzzball formation under different prepreg tensions and feed rates in a static environment with constant temperature and humidity. These tests enabled real-time visualization of the fuzzball growth process. We then performed a quantitative analysis of the initiation and steady state growth phases. Our measurements showed that fuzzball growth rate scales with a power-law function of growth duration, feed rate, and prepreg tension. Additionally, we extended our investigation to full AFP operations, focusing on the effects of path curvature. By applying the same quantitative evaluation method, we found that fuzzballs grow more rapidly as the radius of curvature decreases. This curvature effect was further characterized in terms of the contact angle between the feeding channel and a prepreg tape, revealing a strong correlation with fuzzball formation.

1 INTRODUCTION

In modern aircrafts such as the Boeing 787 and Airbus A350, carbon fiber composite materials are integral to critical structural components, comprising approximately 50% of the total weight of the aircraft [1]. For manufacturing, initially hand layup was the predominant fabrication method, however, to address the limitations, automated processes such as Automated Tape Laying (ATL) and Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) were soon introduced.

A 2008 Airbus report [2, 3], based on data from Spirit AeroSystems [4], indicated that the actual laydown rate for the Boeing 787 was only 8.6 kg per hour—just 20% of Boeing's original estimate of 45.4 kg per hour [3, 5]. This discrepancy arises because composite layup involves more than just material deposition; it also requires extensive rework to correct imperfections. Boeing's analysis of the 787 fuselage barrel production at its South Carolina facility [6, 7] revealed that machine layup accounted for only 24% of the total floor-to-floor cycle time, whereas inspection and rework contributed to 63% (Figure 1a). Similarly, a 2014 report from Electroimpact [8, 9], a world-leader in AFP technology development, showed that, during part fabrication, 32% of time was dedicated to inspection and repair, 14% to process errors, and only 30% to machine layup (Figure 1b). Additionally, at the Defense Manufacturing Conference 2014, USA, Maass reported 55% of floor-to-floor time is consumed for 37%

inspection and 18% rework (Figure 1c). Consequently, more than half of AFP build time is spent on imperfection repair. This issue strongly motivates research into defect reduction and its impact on mechanical properties.

Harik et al. [11] classified AFP imperfections into 14 categories, with tow gaps/overlaps and wrinkles identified as common defects. Among these defect types, Foreign Object Debris (FOD) represents a unique anomaly [11]. FOD refers to unintended objects that become embedded in a part during layup, such as glove fragments, washers, backing films [12], or foil [10, 13]. These contaminants can degrade component performance by inducing wrinkles and other structural defects [14]. One of the specific FOD, i.e. fuzzball (Figure 2), consists of accumulated composite material—either carbon fiber or resin—that collects on the AFP machine head and is dropped on the part under fabrication, introducing excessive material volume into laminates [11]. Benson and Arnold [15] investigated fuzzball formation during the tape slitting process for AFP using Bismaleimide (BMI) prepregs. Their findings revealed that fiber fragments accumulate on machine components when fibers rub against surfaces in the material path process. The study examined five different BMI materials, all of which produced unacceptable amounts of fuzz despite considerable efforts by material vendors to reduce fuzz generation.

Although several studies on fuzzball formation have been published, quantitative investigations remain limited. This is likely due to the difficulty of evaluating fuzzball formation under standardized conditions, given variations in AFP machines, material properties, layup path designs, material feed rates, prepreg tension, and environmental factors such as temperature and humidity. To enhance AFP composite manufacturing efficiency and ensure component reliability, this research aims to establish a quantitative evaluation framework for fuzzball formation. Specifically, this study focuses on developing a controlled workbench for fuzzball formation analysis, conducting in-situ observations of fuzzball growth during AFP operations, and assessing the dependence of fuzzball growth rates on manufacturing conditions.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and AFP system

For this study, we used a 1/4" unidirectional prepreg slit tape (P2362W-19L:T800S-24K/3900-2C) supplied by Toray Industries Inc. [16]. The prepreg material, featuring a fiber areal weight of 192 g/m² and a resin content of 35.5 wt%, was stored in a freezer at a temperature of -18.6 °C (-1.4 °F) before use. Before each test, the bobbins were allowed to reach room temperature inside a vacuum bag for 24 h. For all tests performed in this study, room temperature and humidity ranged between 17.9 and 24.5°C and 20 and 53% respectively. The experimental work presented in this report was carried out on an Electroimpact AFP 4.0 cell installed at the Advanced Composites Center (ACC) [17], at the University of Washington (Figure 3).

Figure 1: Study on floor-to-floor time distribution for fuselage barrels [10]. a) 787 fuselage barrel AFP performance by Boeing (2012) [6, 7] b) Electroimpact report (2014) [9] c) Estimate at the Defense Manufacturing Conference (2014) [10].

Figure 2: A fuzzball formed on a curved path operation. The scale bar corresponds to 1/4" (6.35 mm).

2.2 Workbench study

The end-effector is composed of multiple components (Figure 4). Through a series of test runs, we determined that the majority of fuzz accumulation occurs at the feeding channel of the AFP end effector module components (Figure 4h, Figure 5). To investigate the fundamental effects of prepreg tension and feed rates, we employed an external module – referred to as the AFP workbench (Figure 6a) to feed prepreps out of the AFP head.

A USB digital microscope (AF7915MZTL by Dino-Lite [18]) was mounted to observe the feeding channel directly. Since fuzz formation is driven by contact between material and fixtures, we intentionally introduced lateral contact between the prepreg tape and the edge of the feeding channel module outlet. In all experiments, the prepreg ran parallel to the outlet edge while being fed straight through the system, as shown in Figure 4f. Feed rate and prepreg tension were varied independently. Feed rates ranged between 2.52 and 10.1 in/s; 8.4 in/s representing our standard feed rate for qualified flat straight layups. Prepreg tension was maintained between 0 and 3.42 lbs, of the upper limit for our AFP system. Notably, no thermal input was applied during workbench tests, as heating typically occurs only during material deposition onto the tool surface (Figure 6d). Our analysis focused on the following observable operation parameters: (1) material feed rate, (2) prepreg tension, (3) layup path radius.

2.3 AFP operation study

We investigated whether the fuzzball formation model on the workbench study can be applied to realistic AFP operation in the same manner. To compare the results, we laid prepreps up on a flat coupon table in the AFP cell. For this case we used the laser heating system because otherwise the laid prepreps frequently get peeled off the tool table, although the fuzzball formation spot on the feeding channel is not exposed directly to the laser. We fed prepreps at the feed rates close to the workbench cases. We also fed at 1.67 in/s, but it showed no apparent fuzzball. To be consistent with regular AFP operations, we followed the basic operation program, at which condition the prepreg tension is linearly decided by the material feed rate (Figure 6c). We also changed the layup path radius to several values: 51.5", 62.0", 70.0", 80.0", and 89.7" (Figure 7). This range was tested because with radii less than 51.5" path radius, we frequently see out-of-plane prepreg deformation on the flat table. On the other hand, if it exceeds 89.7", we hardly see fuzzballs. Due to the difficulty of microscope mounting, we instead used a short focal lens camera mounted on the laser heating module (Figure 6b).

Figure 3: AFP cell at Advanced Composites Center (ACC), University of Washington. (Left) Front overview. (Right) The closeup of the end-effector equipped with 8 bobbins shown while manufacturing a 91 cm × 127 cm (36" × 50") composite plate.

Figure 4: AFP robot end-effector and prepreg-fixture contact configuration for the tests presented in this work: end-effector (a) featuring one prepreg roll spool (b), from which the prepreg thread is fed on to the feeding module (c). The thread goes onto the compaction roller (d) through the feeding channel (e), at which the prepreg contacts the feeding channel edge (g,h).

Figure 5: AFP Robot Module Components. (a) The end-effector feeder front view. (b) The feeder components: cutting module, feeder module, and clamp module. (c) The material path in the feeder.

Figure 6: AFP cell's adjacent components and specifications. (a) AFP Workbench scheme: (A) Overview of the workbench module (B) The workbench feeder module. With an external motor, it pulls a prepreg thread out of the end-effector in the park zone 2. (b) The short focal lens for the fuzzball observation in AFP operation. (c) The relationship between the feed rate and prepreg tension in AFP operation. (All prepreg roll results are plotted.) (d) The prepreg local heating on the 7th channel thread. The bright area is exposed to the laser. It occurs locally in between the prepreg out of the feeder on the compaction roller and the tool table/fixture.

Figure 7: AFP operation path making. (a) Curved path design with VCP [19]. (b) Layup simulation onto the tool table. (c) Top view of simulation result. (d) The prepreg threads laid onto the tool table by the designed operation.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fuzzball formation observation

In the workbench study, we captured the fuzzball formation process and examined its structural evolution (Figure 8). A fuzzball formation begins with the appearance of a white accumulation composed of prepreg matrix material that has been ground or scattered due to mechanical feeding. Shortly thereafter, chopped black fibers become embedded in the resin and are twisted together by the motion of the advancing prepreg tape. This interaction forms a spheroidal mass of resin and fibers that elongate over time. As growth continues, the spheroid begins to twist into a tangled, thread-like structure – commonly referred to as a fuzzball. The fuzzball grows in size and complexity by continuously

absorbing additional resin and chopped fibers. Eventually, it becomes large enough to be caught by the material flow and is pulled away, detaching from the feeding channel. Based on these observations, we categorized the fuzzball growth process into four distinct phases: 1) Initiation: rapid formation and growth of a spheroidal structure, 2) Stable Growth: semi-constant growth while retaining a spheroidal shape, 3) Unstable Growth: transition to an irregular, non-spheroidal morphology, and finally 4) Detachment: separation of the fuzzball from the material flow. In the following sections, we focus primarily on the behavior observed during Stages 1 and 2 (Initiation and Stable Growth), which precede the onset of morphological instability.

In the workbench study, we captured the fuzzball formation process and observed its structure (Figure 8). A fuzzball starts to form with white accumulation. This white part is made of prepreg matrix ground/scattered by the feeding. Then, black chopped fibers are involved in the initial resin, being twisted by the flowing prepreg thread. It forms a spheroidal object of resin and fibers, and that quickly begins to elongate. Next it starts to be twisted again into a tangled thread ball, or a fuzzball. As it keeps growing, the object gets longer and bigger absorbing more resin and chopped fibers, and finally that fuzzball is hooked by material flow and then detached.

Figure 8: Fuzzball growth cycle. (a) Feeding starts. (b) Initiation (A fuzzball seed is formed.) (c) Stable growth in a spheroid form. (d) Starting to be twisted. (Unstable growth starts in a non-spheroidal form.) (e) Keep growing unstably. (f) Twisted again and grow until (g) it gets large enough to be hooked by the prepreg, and then detached.

3.2 Workbench study result

To quantitatively analyze the fuzzball growth process, we plotted the fuzzball major and minor axis lengths against the corresponding amount of fed prepreg material (Figure 9). The results suggest that the amount of material fed is not the primary factor determining fuzzball size. In contrast, Figure 10b shows the aspect ratio between the major and minor axes remains nearly constant throughout growth. This ratio follows a normal distribution with a mean value of approximately 5. Assuming the fuzzball can be approximated as a prolate spheroid with a constant aspect ratio s , the minor axis length l_{minor} is constantly proportional to the major axis length l_{major} , as expressed in Equation (1). Consequently, the fuzzball volume can be approximated using the standard formula for the volume of a prolate spheroid, as shown in Equation (2).

$$l_{major} = s l_{minor} \quad (1)$$

$$Fuzzball\ Volume = \frac{4 \pi l_{major}^3}{3 s^2} \quad (2)$$

The underlying assumption of our analysis is that the rate of fuzball volume growth is proportional to Q , the volume of material removed per unit time as Equation (3):

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{4 \pi l_{major}^3}{3 s^2} \right) = C_{Env.Mat.} Q \quad (3)$$

This relationship includes a proportionality coefficient, $C_{Env.Mat.}$, which accounts for environmental conditions (e.g. temperature and humidity). In this study, $C_{Env.Mat.}$ is assumed to be constant under the controlled test conditions. To quantify growth, we measured the fuzball size starting from the point of initiation—defined as the moment when the fuzball length first begins to increase from zero as (4):

$$l_{major} = \left(\frac{C_{Env.Mat.} Q}{\frac{4}{3} \pi s^{-2}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} t^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (4)$$

$$\because l_{major}(t = 0) = 0$$

To normalize the effect of prepreg tension on fuzball growth, we draw upon principles from Metal Cutting Theory. This theory suggests that the depth of cut a is proportional to the product of powers of cutting speed and cutting force [20]. In the context of our study, these variables correspond to the feed rate and prepreg tension, respectively (Figure 11) This relationship is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{d}{dt} l_{major} = \left(\frac{C_{Env.Mat.} Q}{\frac{4}{3} \pi s^{-2}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \frac{1}{3} t^{-\frac{2}{3}} \quad (5)$$

$$a = C_{CT} V^{a_V} \left(\frac{P}{b} \right)^{a_P} (1 - \sin(\alpha))^{a_\alpha} \quad (6)$$

where b represents the width of cut—equivalent to the thickness of the prepreg tape in our setup—and C_{CT} is a proportionality constant. Additionally, α denotes the rake angle (i.e. the angle between the material and the cutting surface), and a_α is its associated exponent. In the workbench tests, α is assumed to be constant.

Following this framework, the material removal rate per unit time (Q) can be expressed as the product of cutting speed, width of cut, and depth of cut as in (7):

$$Q = V b a \quad (7)$$

By substituting Equations (6) and (7) into the earlier expression for fuzball growth rate, Eq. (5), the following growth model can be derived as (8):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} l_{major} &= C_{L.M.} P^{\left(\frac{a_P}{3}\right)} V^{\left(\frac{a_V+1}{3}\right)} t^{a_t} (1 - \sin(\alpha))^{\left(\frac{a_\alpha}{3}\right)} \\ &\equiv C_{L.M.} P^{A_P} V^{A_V} t^{a_t} (1 - \sin(\alpha))^{A_\alpha} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\because C_{L.M.} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{C_{Env.Mat.} b^{(1-a_P)} C_{CT}}{\frac{4}{3} \pi s^{-2}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

According to this equation model, $a_t = -\frac{2}{3}$, $A_V = 1$ and $A_P = 0.59$ are determined. We plot the growth rate/ $V^{A_V} P^{A_P}$ to t^{a_t} (Figure 12). It organizes the manufacturing condition effects of material feed rate and prepreg tension normalized with the growth duration in fuzball stable growth.

Figure 9: Fuzzball major/minor axis length to log the fed prepreg amount.

Figure 10: Aspect ratio behavior to growth duration. Aspect ratio refers to the division of the major axis length by the minor axis length. (a) The relationship between the major and minor axis length. (b) Fuzzball aspect ratio histogram.

Figure 11: Schematic geometry of fuzzball formation in accordance with Cutting Theory [20]. The rake angle is positive in the clockwise direction.

Figure 12: Major axis growth rate/ $V^{A_V} P^{A_P} V$ to t^{a_t} .

3.3 AFP Operation Study Result

We investigated fuzzball growth behavior during AFP operations along curved paths with constant radii of curvature. The major axis growth rate was normalized using the same parameters defined in the workbench study specifically A_V , A_P and a_t . We plot the normalized growth rate to that in Figure 13 and measured the slopes of each subplot. The slope comparison to path radius is in Figure 14 (Left). The workbench experiments correspond to straight-path feeding, which translates to a path radius greater than 89.7". Notably, we did not observe any fuzzball formation when the path radius exceeded this value. To incorporate curvature effects into the cutting model, we attempted to relate the rake angle α and its exponent A_α to the path radius, as path curvature influences the prepreg's position within the feeding channel and thus alters the effective rake angle. However, due to the small range of observed α , it was not possible to obtain direct quantitative measurements. To address this, we defined the rake angle α parametrically as a function of path radius R , using a characteristic length l_{sp} :

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan\left(\frac{l_{sp}}{R}\right) \quad (9)$$

This formulation satisfies two key constraints: (1) the variation in rake angle is minimal and visually negligible across cases, and (2) following the definition of rake angle [20], $\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2}$ corresponds to zero depth of cut, as the blade becomes parallel to the material surface. The parameter l_{sp} was determined in Figure 14 (Right), however, we found that any value less than approximately 0.3" yielded a good fit to the experimental data. Therefore, we selected the prepreg width of 1/4" as a representative length for l_{sp} . Additionally, we enforced the boundary condition that no fuzzball growth occurs in straight path layups (i.e. as $R \rightarrow \infty$). Based on these considerations, we determined the rake angle exponent to be $A_\alpha = 0.25$.

Figure 13: Major axis growth rate/ $V^{A_V} P^{A_P}$ to t^a_t for curved-path AFP operations and workbench comparison. The workbench plot represents its data for all prepregs.

Figure 14: (Left) Path curvature effect to growth rate. (Right) Evaluation of the rake angle effect to the growth rate. For this case, α is parametrically defined in Equation (9).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the fundamental mechanisms of fuzzball formation during Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) operations. Using a microscope, we directly observed fuzzball formation both in controlled workbench experiments and during actual AFP operation. In the workbench study, we quantified the fuzzball size and growth duration under various feed rates and prepreg tension levels. The results, interpreted through the framework of Metal Cutting Theory, revealed that the fuzzball growth rate is proportional to the product of power functions of growth duration, feed rate, and prepreg tension. In the AFP operation study, we extended this evaluation method to examine the influence of path curvature. The results quantitatively demonstrated that increased curvature (i.e. smaller path radius) leads to faster fuzzball growth. Through this combined analysis, we evaluated how key manufacturing parameters—prepreg tension, feed rate, and path curvature affect fuzzball growth rate. This framework

offers a basis for quantitatively predicting fuzzball formation behavior, and it can be extended to incorporate material-specific and environmental effects. Such predictive capabilities are critical for improving the producibility and reliability of composite components fabricated in AFP. Future work will focus on extending this study to the effects of temperature and humidity leveraging the new upgraded AFP cell at the UW Advanced Composites Center (ACC). Furthermore, computational work leveraging quasibrittle fracture mechanisms [21] frameworks such as the microplane model [22, 23] and the Discrete Model for Composites (DM4C) [24, 25, 26] is ongoing to be able to predict some of the constants identified in this work.

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